

ISic2980

I.Sicily inscription 2980

Language

Latin

Type

prayer

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

contrada Furmica, 10km east of Palazzolo

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2251

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175484

1. [p]lura [fa]cias [et]

2. meliora aedif[i]-

3. ces. amen

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645333

PHI 175484

Bibliography

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L.

(eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.51 tav.39

Orsi, P. 1931. Epigrafe cristiana di Palazzolo Acreide (Acræ). Contributo alla storia dell'altipiano acreide nell'antichità. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 8: 287-299. At 297 no.7 fig.3 = Orsi (1942) 212 no.8 fig.108

Ferrua, A 1943-1944. Sicilia Bizantina. *Epigraphica*. 5-6: 85-100. At 98

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1953. Palazzolo Acreide. Epigrafi cristiane nella collezione Iudica. *Notizie degli Scavi di Antichità*. 345-352. At 351 no.8

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